

IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLY (METHYL METHACRYLATE) THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to investigate the low velocity impact behaviour and damage patterns of carbon fibre reinforced methyl methacrylate composites. The process of low-velocity impact damage in composite was simulated using the finite element method and experimentally verified. Orthotropic plane stress conditions of homogenized continuum lamina were used to model composite structure. The evolution of damage was simulated using the finite element code LS-DYNA by material models MAT58 based on Matzenmiller's damage mechanics model with four Hashin's failure criteria and MAT54 based on four failure criteria by Chang-Chang. Damage variables were determined performing calibration of numerical model according to the experimental results of three-point bending and impact tests. Detailed quantitative comparisons were carried out between delaminated areas simulated by the model and those characterized experimentally by ultrasonic C-Scan method. The results of the numerical analyses demonstrate good agreement with experimental data.

1 INTRODUCTION

The low-velocity transverse impact could cause various damages, such as matrix cracks, delamination and fibre breakage [1]. Such damages influence on the significant reductions of strength and stiffness of the materials and are difficult characterized.

The damage mechanism of laminated composites under impact loading can be defined as intralaminar damage such as fibre and (or) matrix debonding or fibre fracture, matrix cracking or plasticity; and interlaminar failure, which develops at the interface between adjacent plies in the form of debonding between layers, so called delamination [2]. Such type of damage is very difficult to predict and the number of various approaches based on failure criteria were proposed for fibre reinforced plastic composites [3-6].

Commercially available codes such as LS-DYNA, ABAQUS, and others, offer material models which utilize a different modelling strategy, include failure criterion, degradation scheme, material properties, and usually a set of model-specific input settings that are typically needed for the computation but do not have an immediate physical meaning [7]. The constitutive materials models can be divided in two main groups: progressive failure models (PFM) and continuum damage mechanics models (CDM). For composite materials the LS-DYNA offers both PFM (MAT22, MAT54 and MAT55) and CDM (MAT58 and MAT162) material models [8].

The authors of this paper are presented some studies for damage analysis of real structures and constructions made from sandwich composites, eg. plates, used in civil engineering or cylindrical structures used for pipes and tanks [9-11].

In this work, the well-known fracture criteria were used to simulate impact behaviour of fiber-reinforced thermoplastics composites (FRTC) using finite element code LS-DYNA.

The aim of the present study was to investigate the low velocity impact behaviour and damage patterns of carbon fibre reinforced methyl methacrylate composites, to simulate the process of low-velocity impact damage in composite using finite element method and to verify the simulation experimentally.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Methyl methacrylate (MMA) resin was used for investigations. Benzoyl peroxide (BPO) was used as initiation system in the free radical polymerization. The fabric used was twill-weaved carbon fabric (CF).

BPO was incorporated in to MMA at weight ratio of MMA: BPO = 100:1. The composite samples were obtained by hand lay-up process of carbon fabric with MMA monomer. Composite code was $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_5$ and thickness 3 mm.

2.2 Mechanical properties

Poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) tensile tests were carried using universal testing machine H25KT with load cell of 1 kN and a cross-head speed of 20 mm min⁻¹. Measurements were performed with the specimens having gage area of 10 mm × 10 mm. The six test pieces were tested for each set of samples. Obtained mechanical properties of composite CF/PMMA and resin PMMA separately are presented in Table 1.

Mechanical property, unit	Material	
	CF/PMMA	PMMA
Longitudinal and transverse Young modulus, E_1, E_2 , GPa	28.6	0.755
Shear modulus, G_{12}, G_{23} , GPa	9.60	0.290
Poisson ratio, ν_{12}	0.30	0.30
Longitudinal and transverse tensile strength, X_T, Y_T , MPa	640	29.0
Longitudinal and transverse compressive strength, X_C, Y_C , MPa	400	29.0
In plane shear strength, S_{12} , MPa	40.0	16.0
Longitudinal and transverse tensile and compressive failure strains, $e_{11T}, e_{22T}, e_{11C}, e_{22C}$	0.045	0.036
Shear failure strain, e_{12}	0.16	0.36

Table 1: Mechanical properties of CF/PMMA and PMMA.

2.3 Impact test

The low velocity impact tests were performed according to ISO 6603-2 by impact tester EL-99 (Zipor-Pegasil). The impact system incorporates 25 kg hemispherical impactor having a diameter of 25 mm. The specimen with dimensions of 140 mm × 140 mm was clamped between two steel plates with a central circular cut-out of 100 mm. The required impact energy was delivered by adjusting the initial height of the impactor. The composite was impacted at a velocity of 1.77 m/s, generating impact energy of 40 J.

2.4 Ultrasonic inspection (C-scan)

For the identification of the delamination in the composite plates, ultrasonic inspection (C-scan) was used. The test method was based on air-coupled ultrasonic technique [13-14]. The air-coupled ultrasonic measurement method has a great potential for investigation of delamination type defects of layered composites. An important advantage of this technique is that investigations can be performed without couplants and therefore various materials that can absorb liquids can be tested.

For the quantification of the damaged area of composite in the C-scans image, MathCad software was used.

3 MODELLING

3.1 Modelling of CFRP composite damage

The finite element code LS-DYNA v.971 R7.0.0 was used to model the impact behavior of CFRP composite. It is known that mechanical behavior of modeled structure very depends upon material model properties especially under the ultimate loading conditions.

Failure criteria were applied for every ply of CF/PMMA composite separately. Plies were assumed to be homogenous and orthotropic (transversely isotropic). For the prediction of composite behavior under loading the failure criteria were applied for every individual ply.

CF/PMMA composite structure was modelled with one part. The bonding between laminas was modelled by embedding additional matrix layers which properties for the numerical model were defined as the mechanical properties of PMMA resin. The thickness of this resin layer for FE model was assumed to be 1 μm . For PMMA layer the PFM model MAT54 was adopted. Using MAT54 model, after the fracture criterion of the ply is exceeded the properties are immediately dropped to zero and the element is deleted. Such modelling gives composite behavior similar to debonding phenomena. CF/PMMA plies were modelled using CDM model MAT58. This material model includes continuous fracture that is after the fracture criterion of the ply is exceeded the elastic properties are continuously decreased.

For the verification of the material models and failure criteria of CFRP three point bending was modelled (Fig. 1) and the result of it was compared with experimentally obtained data. All conditions, including dimensions, loading, constraints were the same as in the experimental tree point bending test.

Figure 1: FE modelling of tree point bending.

The comparison of results of three point bending test and simulation is presented in Fig. 2. This is a final result after the FE model calibration by trial and error. The model calibration was done for LS-DYNA settings obtaining and materials models verification looking for the good correlation with the experimental results.

3.2 Impact behaviour modelling

After FE model calibration on tree point bending, the numerical model for the evolution of damage of composite under impact was created (Fig. 3.). All conditions were the same as in the experimental impact test. The bottom supporting plate in the FE model was rigid and constrained. The force of 4 kN was applied for the top supporting plate to imitate used conditions in the experimental test. The impactor was modelled as rigid; the applied velocity was 1.77 m/s and mass 25 kg.

Figure 2: FE modelling of tree point bending.

Figure 3: FE modelling of impact.

4 RESULTS

The damaged surface views of CF/PMMA composite plates subjected to 40 J impact are presented in Fig. 4. The visual inspection of impacted specimen showed (Fig. 4, a) that the damage appears not only in the impacted zone but throughout the sample area. The biggest fibre breakage is visible in the bottom (non-impacted side) of CF/PMMA composite. Measured damage width and length in the bottom layer are 31 mm \times 31 mm and damage area assumed to be as a rectangle is equal to 961 mm². The internal damage area of the impacted CF/PMMA composite obtained by the air coupled ultrasonic technique and converted to easier understandable black-and-white pattern using software is presented in Fig. 4., b. It is seen that damaged area is not as rectangle; it is as a circle and equal to 1551 mm². This means that real damage area is higher than that one which can be measured by visual inspection. FE modelling confirmed ultrasonic C-scan image result. In Fig. 4., c it is shown damage predicted in the bottom woven layer. The damage intensity is shown in colours; undamaged material is red and its fringe level is equal to one. Broken material is shown as deleted element white colour. The shape of

Figure 4: Damaged surface views of CF/PMMA composite plates subjected to 40 J impact: photo of the bottom surface (a), ultrasonic C-scan image [15] (b) and damage predicted by the FE model (c).

damaged area is similar to the circle as it was in the case of ultrasonic measurement. All damaged elements which demonstrated the lower fringe level then one formed area equal to 1590 mm². This result demonstrates very good agreement with C-scan result, the difference does not exceed 3 %.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The low velocity impact behaviour and damage patterns of carbon fibre reinforced methyl methacrylate composites were investigated by experimental and numerical methods. The finite element model for damage evaluation was verified and presented in this study. It was obtained that this model allows to simulate the process of low-velocity impact damage in composite and to predict damage peculiarities.

It was found that it is not possible to predict damage area only from visual inspection. Due to delamination and fibre breakage the real damage area is bigger and this was proved by ultrasonic measurement. The same result was demonstrated by finite element modelling. The difference from C-Scan did not exceed 3 %.

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